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Two New Inscriptions from the Western Necropolis of Nikomedeia

Nikomedeia Batı Nekropolis'inden İki Yeni Yazıt

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Abstract: A rescue excavation by the Directorate of the Kocaeli Museum of Archaeology and Ethnography was conducted between 2017 and 2019 in the area where the General Directorate of Izmit Water and Sewerage Administration is located. In the course of these excavations, a new *necropolis* area was discovered, including five *in situ sarcophagi*, 51 tile tombs, and two *amphora* tombs. Among them, four *sarcophagi* bear funerary inscriptions dating from the Roman period. This paper presents two of these: 1) The tomb of Aurelius Sosianus Asklepiodotos and his family, 2) The tomb of Hermogenes.

Keywords: Nicomedia, Bithynia, Epitaph, Architecture, Stonemasons and Carpenters Guild

Öz: İzmit Su ve Kanalizasyon İdaresi Genel Müdürlüğü'nün bulunduğu alanda Kocaeli Arkeoloji ve Etnografya Müzesi Müdürlüğü tarafından 2017-2019 yılları arasında bir kurtarma kazısı yapıldı. Bu kazılar sırasında, içerisinde 5 *in situ* lahit, 51 kiremit mezar ve iki *amphora* mezarı bulunan yeni bir nekropol alanı keşfedilmiştir. Lahitlerden dördü üzerinde ise Roma dönemine tarihlenen mezar yazıtları tespit edilmiştir. Bu makalede, bu yazıtlardan ikisi tanıtılmaktadır: 1) Aurelius Sosianus Asklepiodotos ve ailesinin mezarı, 2) Hermogenes'in mezarı.

Anahtar sözcükler: Nikomedeia, Bithynia, Mezar Yazıtı, Mimar, Taş Ustası ve Dülgerler Loncası

In April 2017 during foundation excavations for a building in the Serdar neighbourhood of Izmit, Kocaeli, at the southern border of the D-100 Motorway, at no.59 Sekapark, in the area where the General Directorate of Izmit Water and Sewerage Administration (ISU) is located, archaeological remains of material culture were discovered. A rescue excavation was subsequently conducted in the area by the Directorate of the Kocaeli Museum of Archaeology and Ethnography. During these excavations between 2017 and 2019, 5 *in situ sarcophagi*¹ surrounded by a *necropolis* wall, one of which is without inscription; 51 tile tombs and two *amphora* tombs; 99 coins, 12 terracotta artefacts, eight glass artefacts, two metal artefacts, two stone artefacts and one bronze idol were unearthed². This group of sarcophagi does not belong to a family and they are not related to each other. Therefore, two inscriptions from the area are examined in detail below because their sim-

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¹ We would like to thank the former director of the Museum, Mr Rıdvan Gölcük (now at Troia Museum), who informed us about the inscriptions and permitted us to study them. We would also like to thank archaeologists Kemal Çibuk (now at Troia Museum) and Zuhul Uykul and other museum staff who helped us during this work. We thank the current director of the Museum, Mr Serkan Gedük and also, Prof. G. Petzl for his suggestions.

² Uykul *et al.* 2019, 139-156; Çoban & Avşar 2019, 171-186; Gölcük *et al.* 2020.

ilar in context³. The other two inscriptions are being prepared to be published as two separate papers⁴.

The newly discovered *necropolis* area is located about 700 m from the city gate, on a terraced area 6-8 m above sea level⁵. The necropolis shows characteristics of the stonework particular to Late Roman-Early Byzantine style; this wall is about 11 m long and 60-80 cm wide in an eastern direction⁶. The existence of this wall was already known when another *sarcophagus* was discovered close to the excavation area in 1972⁷. The inscriptions of all four *sarcophagi* located within the wall face southwards, indicating that the road entering the city passes through the south of the *necropolis*.

The inscriptions and the unearthed archaeological materials show that the *necropolis* was intensively used during the IInd-IVth centuries A.D.⁸. The coins recovered in the necropolis area are especially significant for our dating. According to the 23 coins that could be dated from a total of 99; the earliest date for the use of the *necropolis* is the reign of Severus Alexander (222-235 A.D.), while Constantius II's reign (337-361 A.D.) seems to be the latest⁹.

The existence of an extant *in situ necropolis* is a great find, with the entire area concealed and protected due to a large-scale landslide. There could be only one reason for such a large necropolis being buried underground, a large earthquake. Indeed, the latest coins discovered in the *necropolis* are those minted during the reign of Constantius II (337-361 A.D.) and are vital for our dating. Three devastating earthquakes centered in Nikaia, and then Nikomedeia during his reign took place. It is possible that during or in the aftermath of one of these earthquakes, the *necropolis* was wholly buried underground.

Date	Intensity	Location
24.VIII.358 AD	VII	Nikaia
XI.359 AD	VI	Nikomedeia
2.XI.362 AD	VI	Nikomedeia

These inscribed sarcophagi and other finds, which survive to this day, allowed us to learn new things about both the city and the Eastern Mediterranean World.

1. The Tomb of Aurelius Sosianus Asklepiodotos and His Family

An *in situ sarcophagus* with its lid, made of marble, resting on a platform. All sides of the *sarcophagus* are levelled and smoothed; the lid is elaborately decorated. A *paterna* motif is on the right corner of the lid facing the road and an acroterion motif on the left corner. On the narrow right-hand side, there is a *paterna* and a stylized flower motif. On the top section of both side surfaces, clamp holes show how the lid and the *sarcophagus* were bound together. Within the *sarcophagus*, the remains of six skeletons, four glass fragrance bottles, two of which are broken, two partially legible coins, and one wooden two-holed half-moon shaped scone were found¹⁰. The in-

³ The inscriptions were hastily recorded during the excavation works conducted in the *necropolis* area in 2017 and published as a preliminary report with their Turkish translations (Öztürk & Demirhan-Öztürk 2019, 135). In this article, they are republished in greater detail with information the previous report lacked.

⁴ One is in print, entitled: "From Dacia Minor to Nicomedia: Iconography, Onomastics and a New Career of the Late Roman Army: The Sarcophagus of the protector divini lateris Tziampo". *AClassMed* 4 (2021).

⁵ Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 120.

⁶ Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 121.

⁷ TAM IV.1 239. See also: Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 121.

⁸ Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 120.

⁹ Uykul *et al.* 2019, 150-154; Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 125.

¹⁰ Gölcük *et al.* 2020, 123.

scription is located on the side facing the road. Covering the entire front side, the size of the first and third lines of the inscription are carved relatively larger.

Dimensions: Coffin: H: 86 cm W: 2.22 m; D: 1.01 cm; LH: 3.7-10 cm; Line gap: 1.6 cm; Lid: H: 62 cm; W: 2.05 m; D: 1.13 m

Record: H. S. Öztürk & E. Demirhan-Öztürk; **Photo:** Kocaeli Museum of Archaeology and Ethnography

Dating: After 212 A.D. (due to the Aurelius gens)

Αύρ(ήλιος) Σωσιανός Ἀσκληπιόδοτος

ἀνενωσάμην τὴν προγονικὴν μου πύελον ἑμαυτῶ καὶ τῆ συνβίῳ μου Αύρ(ηλία)

Χ vac. ρ vac. η vac. σ vac. τ vac. ε vac. ζ vac. ν vac. η vac.

- 4 Αύρ(ήλιος) Ἀσκληπιόδοτος ὁ κέ Παρηγόριος ἀρχιτέκτων ὕ φύλαρχος) · τῆς κρα(τίστης) · φυλῆς Ματιδιανῆς ἀνενωσάμην τὴν τῶν γονέων μου πύαλον καὶ ἐπέγραψα · vac.

ἑμαυτῶ καὶ τῶ γλυκυτάτῳ μου · τέκνῳ Παρηγορίῳ ζήσαντι ἔτη · ε'· κέ τῆ γλυκυτάτῃ μου συμβίῳ Αύρ(ηλία) · Σευήρα · εἰ δέ τις ἕξωθεν τοῦ γένους μου τολμήσει

τεθῆναι,

- 8 δώσει προστίμου τῆ φυλῆς X μύ(ρια) α', τῶ δὲ συνεδρίῳ τῶν δομοτεκτόνων κέ λιθουργῶν X,ϵ

vacat χ vac. α vac. ζ vac. ρ vac. ε vac. τ vac. ε vacat

8 κέ = καί.

Translation: (I) Aurelius Sosianus Asklepiodotos renovated this ancestral tomb for myself and my spouse Aurelia Khrestine. The powerful phylarkhes of phyle Matidiane, (I) Aurelius Asklepiodotos, also known as architect Paregorios, have renovated the tomb of my parents; (have) inscribed for myself, for my beloved son Paregorios, who died at the age of 5 and for my beloved wife, Aurelia Severa. Whoever commits the crime of interring someone other than a descendant of mine should pay 10.000 denarii to the phyle and 15.000 denarii to the carpenters and stonemasons guild. Farewell!

1: Σωσιανός is a Latin *agnomen*. The name is here documented in the city of Nikomedeia and in the region of Bithynia for the first time.

3; 6: Παρηγόριος. The name is here attested for Nikomedeia and in the region of Bithynia for the first time. Previously attested in Galatia and Phrygia regions four times, people with the name Paregorios had the *gens Aurelius* as well. The Paregorios in our inscription is also an Aurelius.

3: Ἀρχιτέκτων: This title is here attested for the first time in Nikomedeia and in Bithynia¹¹ for the third time. Apart from Nikomedeia, a citizen of Nikomedeia and Tomis from Pontic Olbia, an *arkhitekton* whose name is unknown, were previously attested¹².

4: Χρηστεινή = Χρηστίνη. For –ει’s transformation to –ι, see Gignac, 1976, 190; 249.

The name Khrestine to date has been documented three times in Bithynia; once in Byzantion and twice in Nikomedeia¹³.

6: Ἡ φυλή Ματιδιανῆς: This *phyle*, documented for the first time from Nikomedeia, carries the name of the mother-in-law of Emperor Hadrianus, Matidia. Salonia Matidia alias Matidia Maior, was the mother of Traianus’ niece and Hadrianus’ wife, Sabina¹⁴, and member of Traianus’ household¹⁵.

Honoured by Hadrianus on August 29, 112 A.D. as *Matidia Augusta divae Marcianae filia*, Salonia Matidia died before December 23, 119 in Rome and was afterwards deified as *Diva Matidia*¹⁶. Hadrianus constructed a temple for Salonia Matidia called *templum Matidiae* and also a *phyle* in the Egyptian city Antinoupolis was named after her, φυλή Ματιδία¹⁷. It is possible that Matidia’s name was given to other *phylai* as well; however, it was challenging to make such a suggestion without any hard evidence to date. Due to this newly discovered funerary inscription, we may now think there might be *phylai* named after Matidia in other cities.

There could be two possible dates for using Matidia's name given to a *phyle* in Nikomedeia. First, it could be from the time of Matidia’s death in April 119 A.D.. Or it could be 121-122 A.D.¹⁸, when Nikomedeia was devastated by an earthquake with the intensity of VII and for which Hadrianus allocated great funds for the city's reconstruction, and that’s why the cities of Nikomedeia and Nikaia began to use the title “Hadriane” next to the name of their respective cities¹⁹. It is possible that in return for Hadrianus’ generosity, the Nicomedians might have named a newly established neighbourhood after Matidia. In Nikomedeia, apart from the *phyle* of Matidiane, there is a *phyle* of Hadriane, named after Hadrianus²⁰. Therefore, both *phylai* of Matidiane and Hadriane should be new neighbourhoods established after the earthquake with the intensity of VII of 121-122.

Apart from these two named neighbourhoods, there are other *phylai* known from Ni-

¹¹ The other two *arkhitekton* are known from Nikaia. See *INikaia* 1231; 1256. See also Hellmann 1994, 155, no. 11; 168, no. 53.

¹² *IOSPE* 174. See also Hellmann 1994, 154-155, no. 9.

¹³ *LGPN* IV; VA s.v. Χρηστίνη.

¹⁴ Kienast *et al.* 2017⁶, 121.

¹⁵ Kienast *et al.* 2017⁶, 121. See also *PIR*² 367 s.v. Matidia.

¹⁶ *Hist. Aug. Hadr.* ix 9; xix 5; *CIL* 2080; 3579; *RIC* II 425b. See also Jones 2004, 266-273; Petolescu 2018, 163-165. For detailed information, see also, Kunnert 2019, 74-78.

¹⁷ *Pap. Faijum BGU* 1022 (according to the papyrus dating 192 A.D.). See also *PIR*² 367 s.v. Matidia.

¹⁸ For the date suggested by seismologists, see Ergin *et al.* 1967, 12.

¹⁹ Euseb. *Chron.* vii 1, 198. 10; vii 2, 591; *Chron. Pasch.* 475, 8. See also Ruge 1936, 474; Robert 1978, 396-397; Mitchell 1987, 351.

²⁰ *TAM* IV.1 40. See also, Kunnert 2019, 75.

komedeia, such as Antoniane²¹, Asklepias²², Dia²³, Hiera²⁴, Plotiniane²⁵, Poseidonias²⁶ and Sebaste²⁷.

8: Ὁ συνέδριος τῶν δομοτεκτόνων κὲ λιθουργῶν: The use of the word Δομοτέκτων is rare and could have several meanings: According to LSJ, it is the name for “a carpenter or a senior official responsible for all woodworking in a ship”. For example, in an inscription from either Abydos or Troas, which was published by *LBW* for the first time, there is one “Aurelius Theophilos” who had the title “δομοτέκτων”²⁸. Having copied and published this inscription for the second time, H. G. Lolling suggests that Aurelius Theophilos is “a member of a guild.”²⁹; while Z. Taşlıklioğlu and P. Frisch think that “Aurelius Theophilos is an architect”³⁰. L. Robert, disagreeing with Z. Taşlıklioğlu and P. Frisch, considerer δομοτέκτω as a “builder”³¹. C. Brixhe, on the other hand, suggests that the word δομοτέκτων means “architecte ou maître d’oeuvre”³². The last person to express his opinion on the subject is C.-M. Hellmann, who stated that, due to the τέκτων (= craftsman) part of the word δομοτέκτων, *domotekton* cannot mean “architect”; and suggests that it should be another, lower-ranking profession, “carpenter”³³.

The position of *domotekton* is here documented in Nikomedeia, and hence Bithynia, for the first time. Yet, on the funerary stela from Nicopolis ad Istrum in Bulgaria of one Gaius Bianoros of Nikaia is mentioned as a “δομοτέκτων”³⁴.

According to LSJ, the word λιθουργός means “sculptor of stone” or “marble”³⁵. The existence of a “stonemasons’ guild” of Nicomedian origin was previously known in Nicopolis ad Istrum from a votive stela: According to that inscription, two people named Maximus and Nikon ... ὑ]πε[ρ] | τῆς συνόδου Νει|κομηδέων λιθο|ξῶν κτλ., *i.e.* erected an altar “for the God Herakles in the name of stonemasons’ guild of Nikomedeia”³⁶. The individuals making the dedication, Maximus and Nikon must be two Nicomedian members of the “stonemasons’ guild”.

It is known from inscriptions that many stonemasons or sculptors from Nikomedeia and neighbouring Nikaia³⁷ worked in Nicopolis ad Istrum³⁸: One Flavius Horimos made an offering to the God Mithras following a dream he had. The artisan that made the altar inscribed on its lower

²¹ TAM IV.1 329.

²² MAMA III 263.

²³ TAM IV.1 327; 366.

²⁴ TAM IV.1 258.

²⁵ TAM IV.1 238.

²⁶ TAM IV.1 167; 223; 260; 299. The *Phyle* of Poseidonias got its name from God Poseidon due to Nikomedeia’s relation with the sea and earthquakes. For the Poseidon cult in Nikomedeia, see also Asheri 1978, 95, fn. 9. The *phylai* of Dia and Hiera, which it is suggested originated in the Hellenistic period, must connect with Zeus and Demeter (Kunnert 2019, 75).

²⁷ Öztürk & Demirhan-Öztürk 2019, 135.

²⁸ *LBW* 1743.

²⁹ Lolling 1881, 227-228: “... Ich sehe in Aur. Theophilos das Mitglied einer Handwerkerinnung ...”

³⁰ Taşlıklioğlu & Frisch 1975, 222-223, no. 2: “Theophilos was an architect ...”.

³¹ *BE* 1976, no. 563: “... : Αύρ. Θεόφιλος Μυτιληναῖος δομοτέκτων (nous entendons « maçon » plutôt qu’« architecte ») ...”.

³² *BE* 1995, no. 464.

³³ Hellmann 1994, 165, fn. 22: “Si l’on peut hésiter sur le sens de δομοτέκτων, en revanche τέκτων ne peut désigner qu’un technicien du bâtiment d’un rang inférieur à celui de l’architecte, en l’occurrence un menuisier ou un charpentier ...”.

³⁴ *IGBulg* II 690.

³⁵ For detailed information on the subject, see Robert 1960, 32-35.

³⁶ *IGBulg* I 674; Robert 1960, 35.

³⁷ Another stonemason from Nikaia, Cornelius, son of Gaius, is known from a votive inscription from Tavşanlı. See Drew-Bear & Naour 1990, 2023-2026, no. 28; *SEG* XL 1226.

³⁸ *IScM* I 374: ... Φοῖβος Νικομηδεύς ἐποίηι. See also Dana 2012, 257.

corner “Phoibos of Nikomedeia made (this)”.

The reason for the presence of many settlers in Nicopolis ad Istrum from Nikaia and Nikomedeia is Traianus’ resettlement of families from these cities to the newly-founded city of Nicopolis ad Istrum in the aftermath of his Dacian campaigns of 102-106 A.D.³⁹. When the particular need for architects and artisans for the city's reconstruction is taken into consideration, one should not be surprised to find many stonemasons, carpenters and marble craftsmen in Nicopolis.

Nikomedeia was renowned for its marble quarries in the Roman Imperial Period; there was even a sculpture school in the city⁴⁰. In one of the Younger Plinius’s correspondence with Emperor Traianus, he writes that there is a big lake within the Nicomedian territory (Lake Sophon [= Sapanca]) and “marble, agricultural products, timber and other commercial goods are being transported via the routes on the lake”⁴¹.

2. The Tomb of Hermogenes

An *in situ* sarcophagus with its lid, on a platform. All sides of the coffin are levelled and elaborately decorated. The inscription consists of three lines; a bird motif is placed above a branch at the end of the first line (Fig. 1). Within the *sarcophagus* are pieces belonging to two skeletons, a one-handed terracotta pitcher of red clay close to the head side of the skeleton, one mosaic curbstone, one bone awl head thought to have been used as a hairpin, and one terracotta oil lamp, cracked, were found⁴².

Dimensions : Coffin: H: 71 cm W: 2.12 m; D: 77 cm; LH: 9 cm; Line gap: 6 cm; Lid: H: 45 cm; W: 2.18 m; D: 87 cm

Record : H. S. Öztürk & E. Demirhan-Öztürk; **Photo**: H. S. Öztürk; Kocaeli Museum of Archaeology and Ethnography

Dating: Early Roman Imperial Period (due to the pre-Roman Imperial Period characteristics of the letter Z in the second line of the inscription).

Ἑρμογένη τροφίμω

☉ ζήσαντι · ἔτη · η' ·

Ούενουστεινός.

Translation: *Venustinus* (commissioned this sarcophagus) for his foster-child *Hermogenes*, (died) at the age of 8.

1 Ἑρμογένη = Ἑρμογένει | 3 Ούενουστεινός = Ούενουστίνος

1: τροφίμος: This word, meaning “adopted”, is documented for the second time in Nikomedeia⁴³. In another inscription dating to the Roman Imperial Period, an individual named Iulianus commissioned an *ostothek* for his adopted son, Ameinias, who died at the age of 20. Τρόφιμος is also

³⁹ Iord. *Get.* xviii 101. For discussions on the subject, see Poulter 1995, 4-7; Topalilov 2018, 340-349.

⁴⁰ Robert 1960, 35-36; Dana 2012, 257; Avram 2020, 149-150. For detailed information on Nicomedian stonemasons and the marble trade, see Ward-Perkins 1980, 23-69.

⁴¹ Plin. *ep.* 41. For the known and newly discovered marble quarries from Nikomedeia, see also Güney 2012, 183-185.

⁴² Gölcük 2020, 122.

⁴³ TAM IV.1 170.

used as a personal name and is therefore attested frequently in Bithynia⁴⁴.

3: Ούενουστειῖνος is the Greek form of the Latin *cognomen* Venustus; another Greek spelling, Βενουστειῖνος, is also known⁴⁵. This name is here documented in Bithynia and even Asia Minor for the first time⁴⁶.

The studies conducted within the sarcophagus after its opening showed that there had been two burials. The skeletal remains belong to two different individuals, and the bones are found scattered⁴⁷. There is no doubt that one of the individuals is Hermogenes, who died at the age of 8. The other remains must belong to Venustus.

Fig. 1

⁴⁴ *LGPN* VB s.v. “Τρόφιμος”.

⁴⁵ Solin 2011, 161; *SEG* LXI 1628. See also *AE* 2008, 792.

⁴⁶ This *cognomen* is seen in the Mediterranean World see Solin 2011, 161. See also *SEG* LXI 1628.

⁴⁷ Gölcük 2020, 122.

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BE Bulletin épigraphique.

CIL Corpus inscriptionum Latinarum.

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